

An Interactive Arabic Dictionary

Ghaida Rebdawi, Nada Ghneim, Mohammad Said Desouki, Riad Sonbol
Higher Institute for Applied Sciences and Technology
P.O. Box 31983 Damascus, Syria
Emails: ghaida.rebdawi@hiast.edu.sy, nada.ghneim@hiast.edu.sy,
said.desouki@hiast.edu.sy, riad.sonbol@hiast.edu.sy

Abstract—This paper presents the Interactive Arabic Dictionary (IAD) developed at the Higher Institute for Applied Sciences and Technology (HIAST). IAD is an interactive web application based on the "Al-Wasseet" dictionary. It provides the different meanings of words with examples and multimedia illustrations. IAD presents also other related information like associated words, semantic domains, expressions, linguistic tips, common mistakes, and linguistic information. Users interact online with this dictionary to search information about Arabic words. Moreover, expert users can also enrich the dictionary with new words, different meanings, or other related information.

Keywords-Arabic Language Processing, Language Resources, Arabic Dictionary, Interactive Web Dictionary, Monolingual Dictionary.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last decades, a great development has been achieved in the linguistics industry towards a complete human-machine interaction using natural languages. Moreover, Arabic society moves towards the knowledge community emerged the need to work on Arabic language processing in many applications, like automatic translation, spelling and syntax correction, and automatic summarization. Many research projects and coordination initiatives were launched, recently, in this field, in order to integrate the researchers' efforts.

The computerized dictionary may be considered as the basic component that other language processing applications need. There were some attempts towards building electronic dictionaries, but the used approaches ended with digitized unstructured dictionaries. Therefore, researchers and linguists in HIAST had taken the initiative to build an Arabic dictionary that can satisfy Arabic user needs and Arabic language applications, based on the "Al-Wasseet" dictionary [9]. The Interactive Arabic Dictionary on the web (IAD) is sponsored by King Abdul-Azziz City for Sciences and Technology (KACST), and the Arab League Educational Cultural and Scientific Organization (ALECSO).

II. OBJECTIVE OF THE DICTIONARY

Many studies were carried out, under the cooperation agreement between KACST and ALECSO, to specify the main characteristics and features of the Arabic dictionary, such as the "Specification of the Interactive Arabic Dictionary" [1], and the "Conceptual Design of the Interactive Arabic Dictionary" [2]. We have undertaken the analysis of our system based on the mentioned studies.

Figure 1. A snapshot of a detailed information page in IAD.

The Interactive Arabic Dictionary is a Monolingual dictionary (Arabic-Arabic), targeted to Arabic language speakers and learners. This dictionary contains a multilevel knowledge base: morphological level, lexical level, syntactical level, and semantic level. It is also provided with many linguistic statistics useful for linguistic researchers and software developers.

IAD offers the possibility of searching word meaning, extended with a number of illustrative examples (that presents the correct use of the word in Arabic), and some multimedia contents (images, sounds, videos). It also provides many other useful information (see figure 1), such as:

- non standard plural forms, and other derivatives.
- associated words.
- semantic relations, such as synonyms and antonyms.
- expressions and idioms.
- common mistakes.
- linguistic tips.

IAD includes a simplified version of the morphological analyzer developed at HIAST [6][7] that is used to extract the stem of the given word, and a spelling checker that can check the given word and propose correct alternatives. IAD is integrated with the open source system for derivation and conjugation "SARF" [8] sponsored by ALECSO to enable users to derive and conjugate the searched words.

An important objective of IAD is to provide Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) to enable other applica-

tions to use dictionary services.

III. IAD MAIN ACTORS

IAD is designed to allow a real interaction with web users searching for Arabic word meanings. Expert users can also enrich the dictionary with new words, meanings, examples, multimedia, or other related information. From this perspective, it was necessary to design a system that can manage the interactivity preserving the correctness and integrity of the dictionary.

We categorize the users of the system into 4 categories:

- 1) Administrators: the administrator manages the accounts of other users of the system.
- 2) Common users: access the dictionary through a web interface to search for word meanings and other related information.
- 3) Linguists: can suggest the insertion of new words, the update of an existing word meanings, or other related information. To access the system as a linguist, the user should apply for a linguist account (providing a username, a password, and other required information). When the system accepts him as a registered linguist, he can suggest:
 - Adding new entries, and providing meanings and examples.
 - Adding new meaning to existing words.
 - Adding morphological knowledge to dictionary entries.
 - Adding new semantic relations, and associated words.
 - Adding new examples to different word meanings.
 - Updating linguistic and morphological knowledge of dictionary words.
 - Remove inconvenient data from the dictionary.
- 4) Lexicographers: can validate or reject linguists' propositions. Lexicographers can also provide configurations to derive specialized dictionaries. The administration committee of the dictionary designates users to access the system as lexicographers.

However, all the linguists' suggestions (inserting, updating, or removing), will not be applied directly to the dictionary, and need the approval of a lexicographer before integrating them into the data of the dictionary. This is to maintain the data integrity of the dictionary, and to prevent this data from damage, and incorrect manipulations.

More information about use cases diagram and conceptual design could be found in [4].

IV. DATA REPRESENTATION

The lexical entry of the dictionary is a word that could be a verb, a noun, or a preposition. Each entry is associated with a root, a pattern, and one (or more) meaning. The meaning of the word has attributes such as: definition, propagation, domain of use, etymological information, examples, multimedia (voice, image, video), common mistakes, linguistic tips, semantic domain.

If the word is a verb, other information are added such as: infinitive and transitivity. Information about associated nouns, and the semantic characteristics of the subject and object are determined too.

If the word is a noun, other information are added such as: gender, number, and associated verbs.

V. IAD FUNCTIONALITIES

The dictionary provides two main functionalities: one for searching and the other for enrichment.

1) Search Mechanism

IAD offers many ways for searching. **Searching by entry** searches for the meanings and information related to the given word. The searched entry may be one or many words forming an expression or an idiom. **Searching by root** searches all words having the given root and gives the related meanings and other information.

The result of search (by entry or by root) includes the characteristics of each meaning with examples, multimedia, associated words, semantic relations, expressions, idioms, linguistic tips, morphological and syntactical information, and common mistakes. When the search reaches a word meaning, it is possible to make a **semantic search**; search for synonyms, antonyms, or other semantically related entries.

The advanced search option allows to restrict the search on verbs, nouns, prepositions, or expressions. **The derivation and conjugation** is an additional option that allows the derivation and conjugation of a root using the open source derivation and conjugation system "SARF".

The searching scenario is thus the following:

- a) The user enters an Arabic word that can be completely or partially diacritized or not.
- b) The user decides the search type (by entry or by root).
- c) The system tries to match the word with the dictionary entries or roots
 - i) If it finds a match, a list of corresponding entries is displayed:
 - A) When searching by entry, this list contains all possible entries (verbs, nouns, prepositions, etc.) that correspond to the searched word letters and diacritics.
 - B) When searching by root, this list contains all possible entries (verbs, nouns, prepositions, etc.) derived from this root.
 - ii) If the given word does not match any entry, the morphological analyzer is called to determine the stem.
 - A) If the stem exists in the dictionary entries or roots, the system proceeds with the search using the stem.
 - B) Otherwise, the spelling checker is called to suggest alternatives.

- d) The user selects the desired diacritized entry.
 - e) The system moves to a detailed information page containing the morphological characteristics and the different meanings of the word and other related information.
- 2) **Enrichment Mechanism**
Linguists can enrich the dictionary with new words, meanings, semantic relations, or any other information following a mechanism that ensures security, coherence, and integrity. Only registered linguists can modify the dictionary contents. Each linguist must have his/her own account (user login and password). He/she can suggest adding a new entry or modifying an existing one. He/she can suggest adding/modifying all kinds of detailed information related to entries and meanings. At each step of the enrichment process, IAD presents to the user all available related information to guide him/her in the suggestion process. These suggestions will not appear in the dictionary until the approval of the lexicographer who can explore the suggestions and then accept, modify, or reject them. The approved suggestions will be part of the dictionary, and will appear in the results of next search operations.

VI. IAD PRELIMINARY DESIGN

In order to perform the functionalities mentioned above, the system is decomposed into four subsystems:

- 1) **Search subsystem:** used by common users to perform the search queries. This subsystem includes three components: the morphological analyzer, the spelling checker, and the search component. The morphological analyzer is a simplified version of HIAST morphological analyzer discussed in [7]. This is a limited version that extracts the stem of the given word. The spelling checker is a component developed at HIAST for the special needs of the dictionary. It suggests a list of the closest words to the incorrectly spelled word.
- 2) **Suggestion subsystem:** used by linguists to perform the suggestion of adding, deleting, or modifying entries or other related information.
- 3) **Validation subsystem:** used by lexicographers to review the suggestions in order to approve or disapprove them.
- 4) **Accounts Management subsystem:** used by the administrator to handle the accounts and permissions of different actors.

These four subsystems interact with the database which includes linguistic data, data about the entries state (approved, disapproved, pending), and data about users' accounts. Figure 2 shows a diagram of system decomposition and interaction between the different subsystems.

VII. IMPLEMENTATION ISSUES

This system is implemented using n-tiers architecture; all subsystems are divided into four tiers: Persistence

Figure 2. A diagram of system decomposition and interaction between the different subsystems.

Layer, Data Access Layer, Business Logic Layer, and Presentation Layer. In the following paragraphs, we define the fundamental components in each tier and the relationships among them.

- 1) **Persistence Layer:** We implement this tier using Hibernate technology which provides several facilities for data retrieval, data updating, and transaction management. Hibernate enables to generate Java source files to match the structure of the dictionary database based on object-relational mapping specified in its XML configuration files. In this tier, we have two types of files:
 - Java classes which are simple classes that reflect the structure of the database.
 - XML files contain configuration data that provide Hibernate with details about databases schema; it maps database table columns to Java class fields, identifying primary key fields, matching equivalent data types, and specifying relationships (one-to-one, one-to-many, many-to-one, etc.) among entities.
- 2) **Data Access Layer (DAL):** Using persistence layer, it is easy to implement data access layer. We provide a generic class which performs common tasks in data access layer. All other classes in the DAL inherit from this class and add special behavior if any. Moreover, we provide a DAL factory which represents a single interface between DAL and higher layers.
- 3) **Business Logic Layer (BLL):** Due to the complexity

Sound records for examples	Images	Linguistic Tips	Common Mistakes	Domains of use	Semantic Domains	Associated Words	Idioms
All	حناء	حنظل	حرر	حوالة	حب	حن	حيل
Quran examples	مخبرة	حنن	حنجرة	حجاز	حنف	حنط	حرف
In the letter "haa"	حناء	الحندي	حزيران	حكومية	استحل		
	حيل	حنذ	تحرير	حمل			
	حرباء	حنص	حرم				
	محكمة	حنيد	حيوان				
	حمل	حنك	حمد				

Figure 3. A list of examples illustrating some of the dictionary features.

of this layer, we divide it into two sub-layers:

- BOManager layer responsible of managing business objects (create, retrieve, update, delete), and filling them with the related values from different Data objects.
- Service layer integrates between BOManagers to provide several services in the system such as search, morphological analysis, spelling correction.

As in DAL, we add a single interface between BLL and higher layers.

- 4) Presentation Layer: This layer represents the front-end of our application. It consists of several jsp and html pages.

VIII. IAD CONTENT

The current version of IAD published on the site <http://almuajam.hiast.edu.sy/> contains all "Al-Wasseet" dictionary entries enriched from other important traditional and contemporary Arabic dictionaries. Actually, as a paper version of "Al-Wasseet" dictionary was the only available form of the dictionary when we began our project, we started by a work of data engineering for the content of this dictionary. The result of this phase was a database for "Al-Wasseet" dictionary that became the kernel of our Interactive Arabic Dictionary. There are more than 50000 verbs and 75000 nouns. Each entry has one or more meaning, each of them is accompanied by many examples showing its correct use. Examples are extracted from many sources like Quran, Hadith, traditional and contemporary Arabic books. The meaning may also be accompanied with some other information like multimedia, associated words, semantic relations, expressions, vocabularies, linguistic hints, morphological and syntactical information, and common mistakes. A special effort has been done to enrich the entries of the letter "Haa" in order to illustrate all IAD features and characteristics. Thus, many examples and multimedia illustrations were added, semantic domains for many entries were specified, and sound records for all Quran examples were provided. Figure 3 presents a list of examples illustrating some of the dictionary features. The content of the dictionary is always subject to enrichment respecting integrity and correctness constraints mentioned earlier.

IX. CONCLUSION

The Arabic Interactive Dictionary IAD is a success story of collaboration between researchers, engi-

neers, and linguistic experts in HIAST, under the sponsorship of KACST and ALECSO. The Beta version of the dictionary is now available on the web site <http://almuajam.hiast.edu.sy/>.

Future efforts will be dedicated to integrate IAD with a new and more efficient version of the morphological analyser under development at HIAST, in order to have all possible alternatives concerning the root or the stem of the word. We plan also to develop tools to automate the enrichment process from the Web. These tools enable the dictionary to be enriched with examples, other meanings, media, etc. Some researches are undertaken actually at HIAST in order to provide semantic search for the words. We intend also to develop application programming interfaces (APIs) to provide different dictionary services to Arabic language processing applications programmers and researchers.

In order to maintain the integrity and correctness, the dictionary should be supervised by an administration committee responsible of assigning lexicographers and specifying rules for linguists admission.

REFERENCES

- [1] *Interactive Arabic Dictionary (Project Specifications)*, 2008, http://www.almuajam.org/AraDicPlan_3.pdf.
- [2] *Interactive Arabic Dictionary (Project Conceptual Design)*, 2009, <http://www.almuajam.org/tf.pdf>.
- [3] *"Interactive Computer Dictionary" Contract*, <http://www.almuajam.org>.
- [4] Ghaida Rebdawi, Nada Ghneim, Mohammad Said Desouki, Riad Sonbol, *Internal report on the Interactive Arabic Dictionary prototype*, HIAST, Damascus, October, 2009.
- [5] Marwan AlBawab, *Constructing Computer Dictionary*, 2008, <http://www.almuajam.org/Doc/Bawwab.pdf>.
- [6] Sonbol, R., Ghneim, N. and Desouki, M.S. *Arabic Morphological Analysis: a New Approach*. 3d International Conference on Information and Communication Technologies: from Theory to Applications - ICTTA'08. Damascus, Syria, 2008.
- [7] Sonbol, R., Ghneim, N. and Desouki, M.S. *An Arabic Morphological Analyzer for various applications*. Workshop of morphological analyzers experts for Arabic language. Arabic Language Academy, Damascus-Syria, 2009.
- [8] *Derivation and conjugation system "SARF"*, <http://sourceforge.net/projects/sarf/>.
- [9] I. Mustafa, A. H. Alzayat, h. Abdel-kader, M. A. Alnajar, *Al-Wasseet dictionary*, 3rd edition, Alnouri Press, Damascus, 1960.